

"THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LEGISLATION ON NORMATIVE LEGAL ACTS IN THE THEORY OF STATE AND LAW"

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of legislation on normative legal acts (NLAs) within the discipline of the Theory of State and Law, along with its theoretical and practical significance in ensuring the stability of the legal system. Furthermore, it highlights the functions of this legislation in defining the hierarchy of NLAs, resolving legal conflicts, and regulating the legislative drafting process.

The Significance of Normative Legal Acts in Lawmaking

Normative legal acts are universally binding directives issued by competent state authorities and officials. They establish, amend, or repeal legal norms (such as laws, codes, decrees, resolutions, and regulations). Normative legal acts constitute the primary source of law in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Pursuant to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Normative Legal Acts,' enacted on December 14, 2000, a normative legal act is defined as an official document aimed at establishing, amending, or repealing legal norms as generally binding state regulations." [1] The Oliy Majlis (Parliament) of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ministries, state committees and departments, as well as local government authorities and officials possess the authority to adopt normative legal acts in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The primary characteristics of normative legal acts are as follows:

They are issued by a competent state authority in accordance with general principles and adopted through strictly established procedures;

The process of adopting normative legal acts constitutes a product of lawmaking;

Reflecting the very designation of these instruments, normative legal acts embody rules of conduct of a general nature in the form of legal norms;

Normative legal acts are official documents that possess a prescribed form and required legal attributes, including: the official title, document number, the name of the adopting authority, the dates of adoption and entry into force, the place of official publication, and other relevant details;

Normative legal acts possess legal force.

Normative legal acts are subject to the following primary requirements:

The authority developing a draft normative legal act, as a rule, establishes a commission for the preparation of the draft;

Representatives of interested state bodies, scientific institutions, other organizations, as well as individual citizens may be involved in the preparation of draft normative legal acts;

The authority adopting normative legal acts is entitled to instruct several state bodies, scientific institutions, other organizations, or individual citizens to prepare alternative drafts, enter into contracts with them, or announce competitions for the best draft;

The coordination of activities concerning the preparation of draft normative legal acts by ministries, state committees, and departments is carried out by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

The text of normative legal acts shall be formulated in concise, clear, and plain language.(1)

Normative legal acts may specify the legal mechanisms for their implementation, including sources of funding, incentives, rewards, control measures, and other similar instruments. Unless otherwise specified in the text itself, normative legal acts shall remain in force indefinitely.

{1}"Saydullayev, Sh.A. Theory of State and Law. Textbook. T[ashkent]: «Yuridik adabiyotlar publish» 2021. Page 71."

The application on normative legal acts extends to citizens and legal entities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as to foreign legal entities, foreign citizens, and stateless persons within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A law serves as an instrument to consolidate, develop, and regulate social relations considered paramount from the standpoint of the interests of the individual, society, and the state. A law is an instrument of the highest legal authority enacted by the supreme representative bodies of the state. It constitutes the foundation of the state's legal system and possesses supreme legal force over the normative acts of all other state authorities. A unique adoption procedure is characteristic of a law, featuring a specialized legislative process consisting of several stages. These stages comprise legislative initiative, deliberation of the draft law, the adoption of the law, and its promulgation. Based on the essence of the norms they embody, laws are categorized into constitutional laws, organic laws (which are directly adopted on the basis of constitutional requirements), and ordinary laws. Ordinary laws, in turn, are subdivided into codified and current laws. In federal states, laws are also categorized into federal laws and laws of the subjects of the federation. A distinct category of laws consists of emergency laws. Normativity constitutes an essential characteristic and feature of a law. While other forms of legal acts may also possess a normative character, they lack strict statutory force and may instead be short-term or law-enforcement-oriented in nature. The normativity of a law lies in its elevation of a uniform rule to the level of a universal norm, standard, and criterion for all. A rule enshrined in law applies repeatedly as a uniform requirement across all identical cases. The normativity of a law is inextricably linked to the resoluteness, supremacy, and primacy of the state will expressed within it. It is precisely the imperative (subordinating) character of this will that establishes general standards of conduct and behavior through the instrument of law. The laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan are classified into the following groups:

- The Basic Law – the Constitution;

- Constitutional law;
- Law (codes and current laws);
- The Constitution and laws of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

Among laws and other normative acts, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan occupies the primary position. This document determines the organization of state power and the mechanism of governance, and consolidates the foundations of the constitutional order, the economic and social pillars of society, the political system, and the rights and freedoms of individuals and citizens. The Constitution constitutes the core and the legal foundation of the society's legal system and the entire body of legislation. All current laws are enacted on the basis of constitutional provisions and principles, and in the interest of their execution. Laws enter into force in the following instances: upon the expiration of ten days following their official publication, or from the time specified within the law itself or in a specialized enactment concerning its implementation. A law loses its legal force either upon the expiration of its prescribed duration or as a result of its repeal (arising from the adoption of a new law regulating the same sphere of social relations). A law operates in time. This implies that certain laws possess retroactive effect; that is, the law applies to acts committed prior to its official publication. In particular, in Uzbekistan, laws that mitigate criminal and administrative liability possess retroactive effect.

A law also operates in space. This signifies that laws apply across the entire territory of the country. The state territory encompasses the landmass, internal waters, territorial sea basins, the airspace above these areas, and the subsoil within the state borders. Generally, laws are binding upon all subjects within this territory, namely citizens, legal entities, state authorities, enterprises, institutions, and organizations. The supreme legal force of a law is manifested in the following: no entity, other than the supreme representative body that enacted it, can amend, repeal, or replace it with a new one; all other normative legal acts must be adopted and implemented in strict conformity with the law; if any sub-statutory normative legal act—meaning an act based on the law—contradicts the law, it must be brought into conformity with it or repealed; and no entity, other than the body that adopted the law, may additionally ratify it or suspend its operation. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopts normative legal acts in the form of decrees, resolutions, and orders on the basis of and to ensure the execution of the Constitution and all laws. Pursuant to Paragraph 30 of the Regulations of the Presidential Administration, acts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at establishing, amending, or repealing legal norms as generally binding state directives constitute normative legal acts and are adopted in the form of decrees and resolutions. Crucial acts aimed at reforming specific sectors of public life, determining priority areas of the state's socio-economic policy, or establishing or liquidating state authorities are adopted in the form of resolutions. (Appendix 3) Acts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on operational and other current issues are adopted in the form of orders. Non-normative acts (concerning personnel, citizenship, pardons, political asylum, state decorations, military and special ranks, individual matters, etc.) may also be adopted in the form of presidential decrees, resolutions, and orders. An order provides instructions directly to the executors. An order does not indicate the fact that transactions have been carried out and does not serve as a basis for accounting records. An order is an administrative legal act; in

constitutional law, it is issued by the head of state and executive authorities within the scope of their competencies. Decisions of an executive authority regarding urgent and other current matters are issued in the form of an order. Based on and to ensure the execution of the Constitution and laws, the President issues decrees, resolutions, and orders that possess binding force throughout the entire territory of the Republic. In

accordance with current legislation, the Cabinet of Ministers shall issue resolutions and orders binding upon all bodies, enterprises, institutions, organizations, officials, and citizens throughout the entire territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Article 98).

{2,3} Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-682 "On Normative Legal Acts" (Apr. 21, 2021), available at <https://lex.uz/docs/-5378966>.

Legislation on normative legal acts constitutes an essential component of the discipline of the Theory of State and Law, holding significant functional importance in ensuring the systematicity and consistency of the national legal system. The scholarly and practical role of this legislation is manifested in the following key areas:

Strict establishment of the hierarchy of legal force: Legislation formalizes a clear order of subordination among normative legal acts based on their legal force. By ensuring the supreme legal force of the Constitution and the primacy of laws over sub-statutory acts, this mechanism legally delimits the boundaries of the authorities' lawmaking competence. The legal basis for resolving conflicts of law: The establishment of explicit rules for eliminating contradictions between legal norms (including the principles of the supremacy of legal force, the precedence of special norms over general ones, and the chronological order of enactment) ensures the uniformity of law enforcement practice and upholds the principle of the rule of law.

Unification of lawmaking and legal technique rules: The establishment of a uniform procedural order for the preparation, legal expertise, adoption, and entry into force of normative legal acts regulates the lawmaking process. Adherence to the rules of legal technique enhances the clarity and comprehensibility of legal norms, thereby preventing the emergence of legal ambiguities.

Conclusion. Legislation on normative legal acts serves as the foundation for the systematization of sources of law within the discipline of the 'Theory of State and Law.' The continuous improvement of these legislative institutions directly contributes to enhancing the efficiency of legal regulation in public administration and reinforcing the principle of the rule of law.

References:

- 1."The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: O'zbekiston, 2023."
- 2."Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-682 'On Normative Legal Acts,' enacted on April 21, 2021. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/-5378966>"
- 3."National Legislative Database of the Republic of Uzbekistan (lex.uz)."
- 4."Odilqoriyev, Kh.T. Theory of State and Law: textbook. – Tashkent: Adolat, 2018. – 528 p."
- 5."Saydullayev, Sh.A. Theory of State and Law: textbook. – Tashkent: TSUL, 2021. – 248 p."

6."Yusuvaliyeva, R., Ahmedshayeva, M., & Najimov, M. Theory of State and Law. – Tashkent: TSUL, 2019."

7."Saydullayev, Sh.A. Theory of State and Law. Textbook. T[ashkent]: «Yuridik adabiyotlar publish» 2021. Page 71."

